

Hizb-ut-Tahrir

By Michele Benazzo, IHEID-Graduate Institute, Geneva, Switzerland

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Strongly linked to the political thought of the Palestinian intellectual Taqi al-Din al-Nabhani, Hizb-ut-Tahrir originated in the early 1950s between Palestine and Jordan. In the turbulent post-Second World War Middle East, al-Nabhani identified the structural causes of the Arab world's crisis - manifestly evident in the Nakba and the foundation of the Israeli state - in secular Arab politics and invoked the foundation of a group or party actively pursuing the restoration of the Islamic Caliphate. Hizb-ut-Tahrir is now present in the Middle East and North Africa. Since the mid-1970s, it has also been rooted in Southeast East and Central Asia, as well as in Britain, Germany, and Austria. Despite such internationalization, the movement has never gained substantial political weight anywhere due to its uncompromising rhetoric and refusal of democratic means. It is currently banned in most Arab and non-Arab countries, for it is hard to determine the actual size of the movement globally or in the national branches. Al-Nabhani remained the uncontested leader of the group until he died in 1977, followed by Abdul Qadeem Zallum until 2003 and Ata Abu Rashta since then. Typifying Hizb-ut-Tahrir in a clear-cut analytical category is problematic since, despite its self-representation as a proper party, al-Nabhani indifferently used the Arabic term 'kutla' - group - and 'hizb' - party - in interpreting the Quran's relevant sections. Still, in the movement's conceptual backbone, the notion of "hizb" did not have a pejorative meaning as in antecedent Islamic reformists' understanding who, instead, rebuffed political parties as being a byproduct of Western Modernity. Historically, Hizb-ut-Tahrir is a clear byproduct of the XX century's Middle Eastern sociopolitical evolutions. It profoundly resented from both the interwar period and the immediate post-colonial decades. From the latter, distinctly came a vocal anti-colonialism directed against local Arab regimes culpable of having adopted Western forms of government. From the first, al-Nabhani drew inspiration for setting up pyramidal structures and rigid modes of action that closely featured the Syrian and Iraqi Ba'ath parties. In any society in which it is present, Hizb-ut-Tahrir's actions follow a well-detailed five-step strategy designed by al-Nabhani himself. In the panorama of local and coeval Islamist political activism, Hizb-ut-Tahrir represented a sort of 'third way' between classic Islamic modernist groups, namely the Muslim Brotherhood, and radical Islamism, palpably gaining momentum after Sayyid Qutb. Contrary to Hassan al-Banna's organization, al-Nabhani preferred very rigid political activism to grassroots organizations, always rejected democratic participation and refused a "gradualist" approach in favour of a revolutionary rupture as for Qutb. However, opposed to Qutbism, Hizb-ut-Tahrir never endorsed the notion of "jahiliyya" and rejected violent jihadi practices. Al-Nabhani's thought largely remained non-violent, advocating for an intellectual revival of ordinary people instead. Much of Hizb-ut-Tahrir's activities consist of study-circles for the indoctrination of novices and the creation of an intellectual vanguard to make proselytism in society. The restoration of the Caliphate would be consequential to these steps in the movement's vision. Besides clandestinity and state repression, Hizb-ut-Tahrir failed to gain political weight for internal reasons. First, the very rigid structure reduced adaptation capacity in ever-moving sociopolitical scenarios. Second, the proposal of an ideological reformation limited the ability to compete with other political groups endorsing more practical solutions to people's everyday needs, such as Hamas, the Muslim Brotherhood, or Jama'at al-Islamiyya in Southeast Asia. Third, the will to recruit only heavily educated candidates who previously passed through an intense period of indoctrination further restrained the members' size.

Date Range: 1953 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Wider Muslim World and Muslim Diaspora in the West

Region tags: Europe, Middle East, Central Asia, Southeast Asia, Germany, Arabian Gulf, Le Grand Maghreb, Britain, Austria

This "region" represents the areas where Hizb-ut-Tahrir expanded and successfully rooted. Chronologically, this transnational trajectory departed from the Levantine region (Palestine, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, Iraq), proceeded further in the wider Middle East (Turkey, Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, United Arab Emirates) and North Africa (Morocco, Libya, Algeria, Tunisia, Sudan), and then reached Central and SouthEastern Asia (Uzbekistan, Pakistan, Malaysia, Indonesia). By the mid-1980s, Hizb-ut-Tahrir also carved out a space for political activism among the Muslim diaspora in Europe (Austria, Germany, and, in particular, Britain).

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Amnon Cohen, "Political Parties in the West Bank under the Jordanian Regime, 1949-1967", Cornell University Press, Ithaca and London, 1982
- Source 2: Suha Taji-Farouki, "A Fundamental Quest Hizb al-Tahrir and the Search for the Islamic Caliphate", Grey Seal, London, 1996
- Source 3: Basheer M. Nafi, "The Islamists. A Contextual History of Political Islam", (translated by Aslam Farouk-Alli), AMEC (Afro-Middle East Centre), Johannesburg, South Africa, 2017, ch.5

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.newstatesman.com/long-reads/2008/02/party-hizb-tahrir-members>
- Source 1 Description: Given the secretive nature of the group, internal accounts of ex-members are extremely precious to grasp internal sociocultural logics and effective mechanisms. To this day, most of these sources come from the British section of the group. This is an article by Umm Mustafa who affiliated to Hizb-ut-Tahrir, British branch, for a decade since the late 1990s. The document is highly relevant for delving into personal trajectories of affiliation, internal militancy, disenchantment and rejection of the group's ideology and activities.
- Source 2 URL: <https://jamestown.org/interview/al-muhajiroun-in-the-uk-an-interview-with-sheikh-omar-bakri-mohammed/>
- Source 2 Description: An interview with one of the Hizb-ut-Tahrir leader in Britain. Omar Bakri first joined the Syrian branch of the Muslim Brotherhood in his youth and then became an active member of Hizb-ut-Tahrir in Lebanon. After some years travelling in the wider Middle East for either studying or for

escaping regional governments' controls, Omar Bakri arrived in Britain in 1986 and took up the leadership of the local branch. In 1996, he founded al-Muhajiroun after having left the local section of the group. The interview is interesting for a glimpse on the relationships between different Islamist groups in the Middle East as well as for grasping internal organizational dynamics.

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.worldpress.org/europe/2146.cfm>

– Source 3 Description: This source is an interview with the spokesperson of Hizb-ut-Tahrir in Britain at the beginning of the XXI century. Contrary to the first source, it is more insightful to understand the official posture of the group in the Western context and possible changes compared to the Middle East.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: The process of affiliation to Hizb-ut-Tahrir is very rigid and points to the indoctrination of potential members. Although, in theory, the affiliation is regardless of census and educational level, generally speaking, members tend to be highly educated. As for Islamic reformist groups, membership should be intended in more sociological terms with the level of education and knowledge of the group's ideology as gatekeepers of recognized authority

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Membership comes after an oath

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: At least fifteen years old

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Rather than in strictly religious terms, membership is subordinated to a system so intransigent to make it 'ritualized'. Every new member should pass through an intense period of study or indoctrination to adequately internalize al-Nabhani's ideology. For that, novices ("daris") attend weekly study circles, consisting of no more than five people, and one supervisor ("mushrif") who is in charge of explaining the group's canonical works and monitoring the attendance of participants. There is no time limit for concluding the study period but Taji-Farouki estimated it, on the basis of internal sources, between one and two years, with regular attendance, and up to seven years without regular commitment. Every infringement of rules might lead to internal reporting and disciplinary sanctions. Once the candidate is deemed to be ready, he/she has to make an oath and regularly enter in the ranks of the movement.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Hizb-ut-Tahrir never had any systemic political endorsement given its staunch anti-establishment and confrontational posture with Arab governments. Yet, individuals in state apparatuses at times joined Hizb-ut-Tahrir and plotted against their own governments in attempted coup d'état

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– I don't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: There are no clear indications of Hizb-ut-Tahrir members. Cohen argued that between the 1950s and the 1970s, the size of adherents in Palestine and Jordan fluctuated by around seven hundred. Given the ongoing clandestinity it is hard to have reliable estimate

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (actively discouraged-suppressed by larger religious group(s))

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The structure of Hizb-ut-Tahrir is piramidal. At the apex, there is a central leadership. Immediately below, there are provincial committees that supervise local committees and study circles. It is however unclear the degree of effective control of the central leadership over provincial committees in the Middle East. It is equally unclear how the relationships among national branches beyond the Middle East operate. Hizb-ut-Tahrir in Britain is acknowledged to have developed fully autonomously.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: It is unclear how the succession to the leadership work

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Questioning implies incurring disciplinary measures ranging from warnings to complete expulsion.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The term "alterable" does not fully fit in this case. Al-Nabhani's works are not alterable in the sense that do not undergo intellectual reframing. Yet, these texts are present in other languages for non-Arabic speaker members

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Although not formally codified, al-Nabhani's writings published during the 1950s constitute the obligatory intellectual framework for any members/novices. Taji-Farouki also reported a well-defined chronological order for readings in the study circles. There are no reasons for refuting this claim in the case of Hizb-ut-Tahrir in Middle Eastern branches, there are no internal sources detailing that for European, North African, and Asian sections.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: There are no details on that in Hizb-ut-Tahrir's texts and there are no suggestions on specific burial rules for members.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– I don't know

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:
– I don't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
– No

↳ Other formal burial type:
– Yes [specify]: Sea burial might apply based on the Islamic regulation. This is not exclusive to Hizb-ut-Tahrir but a general rule of Islamic burial

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
– Yes
 - ↳ Food:
– Yes

 - ↳ Sacred space(s):
– Yes

 - ↳ Sacred object(s):
– Yes

 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
– Yes

 - ↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Homosexuality

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– I don't know

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– I don't know

- ↳ Other [specify]
- I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
- Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
- No

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
- I don't know

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
- Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
- Yes

- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:
- Yes

- ↳ Done randomly:
- No

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
- Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - No

- ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– I don't know

↳ Other purpose:

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– I don't know

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– I don't know

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– I don't know

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– I don't know

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– I don't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– I don't know

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– No

↳ Generosity / charity:

– I don't know

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– I don't know

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– I don't know

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– I don't know

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– I don't know

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes

↳ Cooperation:
– I don't know

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– I don't know

↳ Moderation / frugality:
– No

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– I don't know

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):
– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– No

- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - No
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Hizb-ut-Tahrir follows the general Islamic fasting prescriptions

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Except Zakat as prescribed by general Islamic rules

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Other than general Islamic praying prescriptions, members of Hizb-ut-Tahrir are requested to actively engage in the group's works (leafletting, attendance or supervision of study-circle, proselytising activities)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Hizb-ut-Tahrir per se does not openly require risk-taking as a criterion for being accepted but given the group's staunch anti-governmental postures and bans, many members were put on trial, jailed, or executed. Risk-taking is then a likely implicit acceptance in joining the movement

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Marginalization is not openly prescribed but is highly likely given the uncompromising interpretation of religious daily predicaments enacted by the group's members

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Other than standard Islamic rituals, for instance, members are required to attend the group's events based on their roles. Supervisors must take part in study circles and members of the different commissions must actively sit in them. Given the current clandestinity of the group worldwide, it is however unclear the frequency and duration of these events.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Notes: In principle, Hizb-ut-Tahrir members cannot adhere to other associations or parties in contradiction to Islam. This does not exclude members from enjoying the resources of national institutions such as famine relief, if present.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Same as the precedent comment

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Same as the antecedent comment

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Hizb-ut-Tahrir typically attracts well-educated individuals who had previously received (or are receiving) formal education from other institutions such as high schools or public/private universities. For instance, in Europe at least, university campuses were crucial hotspots for recruitment.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Hizb-ut-Tahrir originally applied the Jordanian internal minister to formally establishing itself as a local political party. National institutions forbade it on the basis of the group's outspoken rejection of secularism not in line with the national Constitution.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: As for famine and poverty relief funds and care for infirms and the elderly, Hizb-ut-Tahrir's members have in theory access to institutional state services, food storage included, if provided

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Same as in the previous comment

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Same as in the previous comment

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: It is unclear how local branches raise their funds but Suja-Tarouki's analysis based on internal reports claims that each member and novices donate part of its revenues to the group.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Hizb-ut-Tahrir are not exempted from paying local taxes imposed on national legislations

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Here the term interaction applies in its wider meaning. As being banished in almost every country in which the movement is active, the group's members were likely objects of investigations by national police forces.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Rather than judges as individuals, there are judging bodies overseeing over the coherence of members' behaviors with the internal rules. Evidently, the jurisdiction of these judging structures is limited to affiliates and internal issues only.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: The most severe punishments include permanent expulsion which generates similar consequences of ostracism i.e. the total exclusion from the social, political, and cultural capital of Hizb-ut-Tahrir.

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
 - I don't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Hizb-ut-Tahrir's members are not immune from institutionalized forms of punishments based on national legislations

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: See the comment above

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: See the comment above

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: See the comment above

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: See the comment above

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: See the comment above

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In theory, national rules for military services stand for Hizb-ut-Tahrir members and some affiliates were indeed part of the Army. In particular, the complicity of some Army officials and members of the movement's local branch is reported in three attempted and failed coup d'état in Jordan in the late 1960s and early 1970s.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See the comment above

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Al-Nabhani steadily insisted on the use of Arabic for internal communication and, in particular, for the formal education of members/novices. However, pushed by exigencies of recruiting, local branches had adopted local languages at times. For instance, in Britain, Germany, and Austria, formal documents are in English and German respectively.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Hizb-ut-Tahrir follows the regular Islamic calendar

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: As for welfare and transportation, there are no internal rules preventing Hizb-ut-Tahrir's members from enjoying the state's institutional services

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